

Synthesis and Characterization of Some Polymeric Metal-Complexes of Terephthalaldehyde bis-(4-Phenylthiosemicarbazone)

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Chain coordination polymeric complexes $(ML_2 \cdot 2H_2O)_n$ (M =metal ion, L = $C_{22}H_{18}N_6S_2$ and n =degree of polymerization) between Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II), and terephthalaldehyde bis-(4-phenylthiosemicarbazone) (TPBPTS) have been synthesized, and characterized through analytical, spectral (infrared and reflectance), magnetic and thermal studies. The powdery coloured complexes are insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. Infrared spectra show that the ligand molecules act as tetradentate coordinating through the thio sulphur and nitrogen of the C=N group. The metal ion is the bridging unit between the donor sites of the ligand, and the polymeric chain grows through consecutive TPBPTS-metal linkages. Magnetic and electronic spectral data suggest octahedral geometry. The order of thermal stability is: Ni > Co > Cu.

THIOSEMICARBAZONES form coordination polymers¹⁻⁶ with bivalent metal ions. Some of its derivatives have been tried for applications in medicine and a significant correlation between the chelating properties and antitumor activity of a group of heterocyclic aldehydic thiosemicarbazones in animal systems has been noted⁶⁻⁸. Special attention has been paid in the context of their activity against viruses, protozoa, and small pox⁹⁻²¹.

The present investigation is in continuation with the work on coordination polymers in progress in these laboratories¹³⁻¹⁵, and describes the syntheses, general properties, composition, infrared and reflectance spectra, magnetic susceptibility measurements and thermogravimetric analyses of complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) with terephthalaldehyde bis-(4-phenylthiosemicarbazone) (TPBPTS).

Experimental

Materials :

TPBPTS was prepared by the method reported earlier¹⁶. $Co(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Ni(CH_3COO)_2$

$4H_2O$ and $Cu(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot H_2O$ (all of BDH make), and the solvents used were of reagent grade.

Preparation of the complexes :

To the metal salt solution in 25 ml DMF [0.42 g of $Co(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, 0.42 g of $Ni(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ or 0.50 g of $Cu(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot H_2O$] 1.08 g of TPBPTS also in DMF (100 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The mixture when refluxed at 130° for ca 2h, and left overnight yielded the complex, which was filtered, washed once with DMF and then with ethanol several times, till the filtrate was colourless. The product was finally washed with ether, and dried over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator.

Physical Characteristics :

The metal-complexes which are stable and powdery in appearance do not dissolve in water and in common organic solvents viz. ethanol, acetone, benzene, nitrobenzene, chloroform, DMF and DMSO. The colour and temperatures of decomposition are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EMPIRICAL COMPOSITION AND CHARACTERISTICS OF TPBPTS-COMPLEXES

Empirical Composition	Colour	Dec. temp. (°C)	Elemental analyses %, Found (calc)			
			Metal	C	H	N
$[Co(C_{22}H_{18}N_6S_2) \cdot 2H_2O]$	reddish brown	270	11.05 (11.23)	51.42 (50.29)	4.32 (4.19)	17.05 (16.00)
$[Ni(C_{22}H_{18}N_6S_2) \cdot 2H_2O]$	reddish brown	360	10.85 (11.18)	49.43 (50.31)	3.90 (4.19)	17.45 (16.00)
$[Cu(C_{22}H_{18}N_6S_2) \cdot 2H_2O]$	greenish yellow	260	11.15 (11.99)	48.12 (49.85)	4.45 (4.15)	16.15 (15.86)

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Elemental analysis ;

Microanalytical methods were employed for the determination of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen. The complexes were decomposed by HNO₃ and the metal contents estimated titrimetrically against EDTA.

Spectral studies :

I.R. spectra using KBr pellets were recorded with the aid of a Beckman Infrared Spectrophotometer in the range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹. Diffuse reflectance spectra in the solid state were obtained from a Spectrophotometer Model VSU-2 in the range of 200 to 900 nm.

Magnetic measurements :

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the solid complexes were done with a Guoy set up at room temperature 25°.

Thermogravimetry :

TG data were obtained from an assembly capable of producing temperatures upto 800° with a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) agree with the general formula (ML₂H₂O)_n (where M=metal ion, L=C₂H₂N₆S₂ and n=degree of polymerization). The presence of water molecules is indicated by the

loss in weight of the complexes on heating (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Thermal stability of TPBTS-complexes

The observed weight loss is 6.85, 6.86 and 6.79% upto the temperature 240° which corresponds to the loss of 2H₂O. The thermal stability data show that the decomposition of the complexes starts at 270°(Co), 360°(Ni) and 260°(Cu), and the complete decomposition of the organic material takes place at 550-600° leaving a residue of the metal oxide.

Table 2 shows the values of the magnetic moments, significant bands in the reflectance spectra, and the geometry of the complexes.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENT, ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND GEOMETRY OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex with	Magnetic moment (B.M.)*	Position of the bands (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments	Geometry
Co(II)	4.93	24,260	⁴ T _{1g} (F)→ ⁴ A _{2g} (F)	Octahedral
		20,410	⁴ T _{1g} (F)→ ⁴ T _{2g} (P)	
		16,000	⁴ T _{1g} (F)→ ² E _g	
Ni(II)	2.88	26,310	³ A _{2g} (F)→ ³ T _{1g} (P)	Octahedral
		14,290	³ A _{2g} (F)→ ³ T _{1g} (F)	
		13,000	³ A _{2g} (F)→ ³ T _{1g} (F)	
Cu(II)	1.92	14,290	² E _g → ² T _{2g}	Octahedral

*1B.M. = 9.273 × 10⁻²⁴Am²

The structure of TPBPTS is represented in (I)¹⁶. The thione group (C=S) having protons adjacent to it is relatively unstable in the monomeric form, and tends to change over to a stable C-S single bond by enethiolization¹⁷. The infrared spectrum (Table 3)

assignable to C-N stretching vibration of the free ligand shifts to higher frequency region in the cases of the complexes (an additional band is observed near 1700). The shifting of the band towards higher frequency region indicates the increase in bond order

 TABLE 3—BAND ASSIGNMENTS IN THE INFRARED SPECTRA OF TPBPTS AND ITS COMPLEXES (CM⁻¹)

TPBPTS	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	assignments
...	3545 s	3550 s	3545 s	ν O-H
3480 m	3485 s	3470 s	3470 s	ν N-H
3440 w	3435 s	3440 w	3430 w	
3040 m	3035 m	3030 m	3040 w	ν C-H
1680 vs	1700 s	1695 vs	1705 s	ν C=N
	1670 vs	1680 vs	1680 s	
	1615 s	1600 s	1600 s	δ H ₂ O
1590 vs	1590 vs	1585 s	1585 vs	ν C=C &
1550 s	1540 s	1550 vs	1545 s	ν C=N-N
1480 s	ν C=S &
1430 s	ν N-C-N
1340 vs	1340 vs	1335 vs	1325 vs	ν C-N of Ar-N type
1140 s	1130 vs	1135 s	1140 vs	<i>p</i> -substituted phenyl ring
975 s	960 s	900 s	960 s	C-H out of plane
870 s	875 s	870 s	870 s	bending
750 vs	740 w	735 s	735 s	
...	630 vs	650 s	615 s	ν M-N & ν M-S
450 s	535 s	540 s	540 s	δ N-C-N

vs=very strong, s=strong, m=medium, w=weak

of TPBPTS shows an intense band at 1430 corresponding to C=S stretching vibration; and no S-H stretching band near 2570 is observed which indicates that in solid state it remains in thione form (I). However, in solution it is likely to be in equilibrium with the thiole tautomeric form (II).

The spectra of both ligand and the complexes show strong absorption bands near 3480 and 3440, due to N-H stretching vibration. The band at 1680

of the C=N bond, which may arise due to increase in the conjugation of *pi*-electron system. The *d*-electrons of the metal ions are back donated to the orbital of the ligand participating in conjugation¹⁸. The intense bands in the range of 1480 to 1430 in the spectrum of the ligand (stretching bands of N-C-N and C=S respectively), disappear in the spectra of the complexes. This appears to be due to the change in the nature of N-C-N to N-C=N and of C=S to C-S on complexation^{1,4,19}. New bands near 3550 and 1600 in the complexes have been assigned to ν O-H and δ H₂O vibrations of the coordinated H₂O²⁰. The bands in the range of 650 to 535 are due to M-N and M-S stretching vibrations (All wave numbers are expressed in cm⁻¹).

TPBPTS behaves as tetradentate chelating agent, coordinating metal ions each through the thiole sulphur atom and the terminal nitrogen atom of the C=N group of the Schiff base. Coordination polymerization is achieved since steric factors prevent the coordination of all the donors to a single metal ion, which therefore acts as bridging unit between the donor sites of the ligand, and thus the polymeric chain grows through the consecutive TPBPTS-metal linkages (III).

The geometry of the ligand, analytical data, the extreme insolubility of the compounds and thermal stability suggest the polymeric nature of the complexes.

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